

Controversial Issues in Biology: Should we change weather...

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General introduction

The class follows a repeating template of selecting a controversial issue proposed by UNH faculty members, finding 20 research papers on said topic, and encouraging the classroom to engage with and discuss the various papers selected for each topic. 3-4 days were allotted to reviewing and discussing each topic, with each topic of discussion being led by a group of 2-3 students in the class. 10 pro and 10 con papers were selected per topic, reviewed, and discussed. For each paper, three questions were asked about specific details of the article. One paper from each topic was chosen by each student, to thoroughly review the paper and prepare a short summary for the class to discuss, and answer the three questions. This allowed for more intensive understanding of the papers collectively, giving better insight into the topics at hand than if we had just read the abstract/Google search results. The class had an open discussion of each topic/paper, allowing thoughts on each paper to be shared. After reviewing all sources, the class was polled to form a stance on whether we collectively agreed we should enact the topic actions. The vote was on a scale of 1 to 10, with 1 indicating strong opposition to the controversial issue and 10 representing full support. The votes were averaged to determine the class's overall position on the topic.

Why would we control the weather? Who would?

Weather modification is the practice of altering atmospheric activity through human action ([Battan, 2025](#)). This arose from a series of experiments done by Vincent J Schaefer, Bernard Vonnegut, and Irving Langmuir in 1947, who proved that cloud behavior could be altered with dry ice ([Swanson, 2025](#)). This idea has been a topic of interest for humanity for some time, seen in science fiction novels, movies and research fields ([Galperina, 2024](#)). Weather modification is done commonly through cloud seeding as well as supercooled fog dispersal ([World Meteorological Organization \[WMO\], 2025](#)) but can be done inadvertently as well; industrialization does appear to have the capacity to cause weather modification in the area of industrial plants in otherwise urban areas ([NASA, 1974](#)). Solar Radiation Management [SRM] is a hypothetical, proposed additional type of modification in which sun rays are reflected away from the earth in order to combat rising temperatures ([National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration \[NOAA\], 2024](#)). As of this year, this is considered potentially possible with existing technology ([Duffet et al., 2025](#)). It is, however, a temporary “fix” ([Earth One, 2019](#)).

Weather modification is a used defense against climate disasters, as well as a manner through which populations in need can be supplied with access to water and agriculture ([Sovacool et al., 2022](#)). This is a controversial issue, with concerns around it being used as a weapon or having unforeseen consequences being points against its ethical standing ([Imam, 2024](#)). With even some

politicians worried that political parties are using weather control to cause harm to constituents ([Bogardus, 2025](#)), there is significant pressure to be in agreement of how this power could be used.

What are the pros?

Weather control technologies like cloud seeding and solar geoengineering are gaining attention for how they can help protect people and ecosystems. Cloud seeding has been shown to boost water supplies by increasing runoff and supporting natural hydrological cycles that benefit communities and agriculture ([Yoo et al., 2022](#)). Alberta's hail suppression program, which is a long-term project, showed that sustained and well-funded weather modification efforts can succeed with minimal negative impacts ([Gilbert et al., 2016](#)). There are similar successes that happened in Ethiopia rain-enhancement efforts offered a reliable solution to drought and helped farmers ([Wondie, 2023](#)). Not only for rainfall, but geoengineering holds promises on a global scale too, where it is estimated to cut heat-related deaths by 90% by 2080, helping cool the planet with the worsening climate ([Harding et al., 2024](#)). Broader analyses claim that these interventions could have other extra benefits like protecting biodiversity, improving crop yields, safeguarding ecosystems, while also creating jobs and reducing poverty ([Sovacool et al., 2022](#)). Public perception studies show that people, especially in the global south where climate vulnerability is greatest, strongly support these technologies for their potential to reduce disaster risks ([Baum et al., 2024](#)).

What are the cons?

With all the promises the weather control technologies show, critics warn of risks. Public opinion research shows big skepticism toward solar geoengineering and the concerns were mostly about transparency and limited public involvement ([Buck et al., 2025](#)). Cloud seeding has even been flagged as a potential weapon for wars which therefore raised ethical and environmental concerns ([Imam, 2024](#)). Some of the weather control technologies resulted in local conflicts such as in France where hail suppression benefited some farmers but harmed others ([Petit et al., 2023](#)). Speaking globally, solar geoengineering could disrupt rainfall patterns, triggering droughts and instabilities beyond what the models predict ([Hegerl & Solomon, 2009](#)). Others caution that these technologies may worsen inequalities and encourage risky behavior along with distracting from the urgent need to cut emissions ([One Earth, 2019](#); [Corner & Pidgeon, 2014](#)). Therefore, even though the pros of weather control technologies might outweigh the cons, it is still required for us as responsible beings to research and study this area more before proceeding to implementations.

What do we think?

Our group ultimately supports the idea of weather modification as a technology with significant potential, keeping in mind that it could lead to both widespread benefits and unintended negative impacts. We believe it is worth further exploration but only with cautious

and under well regulated laws to minimize risk impacts. However, while such scientific benefits are exciting, we believe that our world is facing more major global challenges such as poverty, famine, public health and climate mitigation, that deserve more urgent attention and resources. This perspective was reflected in our class poll, where the majority of the students rated their support for weather control below 4 out of 10. Overall, we support continued research, but we think society should prioritize solving more pressing issues before heavily investing in such a large-scale weather control plan.

Cons of weather control	Source	Pros of weather control	Source
<p>Public Perception & Social Acceptance: Studies show that the public is skeptical and opposed to weather technologies, with concerns about moral hazards, political instability and risk of misuse outweighing its benefits.</p>	<p>Buck et al. (2025) Corner & Pidgeon (2014) Aronova (2015)</p>	<p>Practical Applications and Effectiveness: Well managed projects show weather control can boost water, crops and disaster control with limited risks.</p>	<p>Baum et al. (2024) Sovacool et al. (2022) Sovacool et al. (2022c) Peek et al. (2021)</p>
<p>Ethical, Legal & Political Risks: Studies highlight the dangers of weaponization, global inequalities and governance gaps, highlighting the urgent need for international regulations.</p>	<p>Imam (2024) Parson & Keith (2024) Earth One (2019) Tsagkaris et al. (2023) Battan (2025) Kwa (2001)</p>	<p>Public Perception & Global Perspectives: Support is stronger in vulnerable regions, where people see intervention as a responsibility..</p>	<p>Wondie (2023) Yoo et al. (2022) Swanson (2025) American Meteorological Society (2010) Harding et al. 2024</p>
<p>Environmental & Scientific Risks: Evidence from studies and real world events demonstrating that weather control can disrupt ecosystems, rainfall and the</p>	<p>Hegerl & Solomon (2009) NASA (1974) NOAA (2024) WMO (2025) Galperina (2024) Petit et al. (2023) Gilbert et al. (2016)</p>	<p>Broader Benefits & Co-impacts: Weather control could cut heat deaths and bring social, ecological and economic gains.</p>	<p>Williams et al. (2020) Impact of Solar Geoeengineering on Temperature-Attributable Mortality (2025)</p>

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Ethical, Legal & Political Risks: Studies highlight the dangers of weaponization, global inequalities and governance gaps, highlighting the urgent need for international regulations.	Imam (2024) Parson & Keith (2024) Earth One (2019) Tsagkaris et al. (2023) Battan (2025) Kwa (2001)	Public Perception & Global Perspectives: Support is stronger in vulnerable regions, where people see intervention as a responsibility..	Wondie (2023) Yoo et al. (2022) Swanson (2025) American Meteorological Society (2010) Harding et al. 2024
ozone layer.			Duffey et al. (2025)

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